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The Effect of Organizational Culture on Turnover Intention in Private Universities in Afghanistan

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Abstract

This study's primary goal is to investigate the link between organizational culture and the variables that affect an employee's decision to quit their present position at Private universities. Employee turnover still is a major problem for companies since it is highly expensive from the organization's perspective and has a substantial negative impact. The majority of the explanations that are mentioned in the literature are conservative views of traditional causes, including sociological and psychological organizational behavior. Organizational culture is one of the traditional factors of voluntary turnover that has been studied but still requires attention. This paper examined how organizational culture affects professional University staff's intentions to leave private Universities. To determine the connection and impact between the independent and dependent variables, correlation and regression analyses were used. The results demonstrate that Type B adhocracy culture predominated in private Universities. The findings showed that there is just one sort of organizational culture that affects intention to leave: Type A Clan culture, it is also shown that this type of organizational culture has a significant and positive effect on voluntary turnover intention among University staff. This discovery may be used by decision-makers and other interested parties that need to find a means to stop professional University employees from quitting on their own and create an organizational culture or policy to keep them employed in private Universities.

Keywords: Clan Culture, Adhocracy Culture, Market Culture, Hierarchy Culture, Turnover Intention.

INTRODUCTION

People with talent are today recognized as perhaps the most significant and precious commodity that provides a business a benefit in comparison to rivals. When a firm employs acceptable measures to retain personnel, it is realized as honest (Pepe, 2010). Given the high cost of hiring new personnel, some businesses view staff retention as a successful investment. Staff members have critical implications that inspire entities to make their own greatest effort to keep professionals and skilled personnel through learning the critical features that affect their work fulfillment and attempting to give them access to an appropriate work situation in order to eliminate the reasons that influence them to resign (Longo, M. & Mura, M, 2007); (Hughes, J. & Rog, E., 2008).

In a lot of sectors, staff turnover was a big problem. Staff turnover has a detrimental influence on a company's efficiency and production, along with size and quality, as a result of the organization's money being diverted (Simmons, 2008). As a result, researching a staff's psychological intents to resign is indeed an important topic in management, since competent retention and staff turnover are key challenges that many companies face.

The culture of an organization is thought to play a significant role in determining its final outcome (Sawner, 2000). This is usually blamed for organizational problems and, occasionally, lauded for producing admirable traits (Baker, 2004; Shani & Lau, 2008). The impact of organizational culture on important employee attitudes, in addition to impacts at the organizational level, is widely established (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Various studies have shown how organizational culture affects employee commitment, job satisfaction, and decision-making (Cameron, K. S. and Quinn, R. E, 1999).

Abundant terms have been used to describe organizational culture. (Ott, 1989). It includes a wide variety of characteristics such as an organization's traditional attire, language, conduct, beliefs, values, assumptions, prestige and authority symbols, myths, rites and rituals, and forms of respect and subversion, all of which influence the character and standards of the organization. Given the diversity of events, it's not surprising that no consensus exists on a single definition of organizational culture, how it should be monitored or quantified, or how different methods may be used to assist routine administration or organizational transformation.

The existing definition, on the other hand, reflects a common view of corporate culture and will serve as a springboard for future discussion. Organizational culture is a collection of widely held, fact-based beliefs and, as a result, are taught to new employees as the appropriate way to observe, think, and feel about problems. A certain group devised, discovered, or developed this as a technique for coping with external adaptation and internal integration challenges (Shien, 1985).

Research Hypotheses

- ✓ H1: Employee turnover is affected by organizational culture.
- ✓ H2: Clan Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.
- ✓ H3: Adhocracy Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.
- ✓ H4: Market Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.
- ✓ H5: Hierarchy Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, a quantitative approach is used to lead the investigation. This study will make use of both primary and secondary data. The primary data was acquired from the target population using a questionnaire (employees of Private Universities). The secondary data, all material related to the themes is used by the researcher. Journals, papers obtained on the internet, textbooks, and other similar dissertations were investigated to supplement the research.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts, a Demographic section, an Independent variable (Organizational culture), and a dependent variable (Turnover intention). To assess organizational culture, this research used the Organization Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) questionnaire as an Independent variable (Sashkin., 1991). The questionnaire created by Roodt was used to assess employee turnover intentions (Roodt, 2004). Employees were asked to assess their level of agreement with leaving their jobs on a five-point scale.

A correlational design was the best option for my study since I am examining the relationship between independent component of corporate culture and one dependent variable, turnover intentions. The data will analyze using multiple linear regressions since the researcher is dealing with four forms of organizational culture as an independent variable and their separate relationships with the dependent variable.

DATA ANALYSIS

In order to find a relationship between the independent and dependent variables, the data were analyzed quantitatively using SPSS (Statistical Packages for Social Sciences). Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, are used to assess demographic elements in the study. Correlational analysis has been used to investigate the relationship between organizational culture and turnover intention. Furthermore, the influence of organizational culture on turnover intention was investigated using multiple linear regression analysis.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is a translation of original data into information that can be easily articulated. It helps the researcher understand, recognize, and change the data by describing its basic properties of the data. To begin data was evaluated the mean scores of the four organizational culture categories. The organization's main organizational culture type is represented by the highest mean score. The outcome is shown in the table below.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Adhocracy Culture	135	2.50	5.00	3.9765	.55201
Hierarchy Culture	134	2.67	5.00	3.8856	.52083
Clan Culture	137	2.50	5.00	3.8564	.49474
Market Culture	137	2.33	5.00	3.9720	.52804

Valid N (listwise)	130				
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Source: own survey, spss output

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's alpha is a fundamental statistic for assessing internal consistency or dependability, and it is within the acceptable range as indicated in the Table below. The study instrument is accurate according to Cronbach's alpha's standard rule of thumb. For the entire set of data as well as each subgroup, the measures' reliability was strong (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.70). The minimal threshold of 0.70 Cronbach's Alpha values is proposed by Nunnally (1978).

S.N	Culture	Cronbach's Alpha
1.	Clan	.82
2.	Adhocracy	.69
3.	Market	.74
4.	Hierarchy	.79

Source: own survey, spss output

Correlation Analysis

Pearson's bivariate correlation using a one-tailed test reveals a negative link between culture types A: clan culture, as illustrated in table. At the 0.05 level of significance, Pearson's correlation result of $r = -.547$ is significant. At $r = .532$, $p = 0.00$, hierarchical culture is also strongly and positively associated to turnover intention. At $p = .00$, market type culture is strongly connected with turnover intent.

Correlations						
		Clan Culture	Adhocracy Culture	Market Culture	Hierarchy Culture	Turnover Intention
Clan Culture	Pearson Correlation	1	.398**	.394**	.520**	-.547
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.069
	N	135	132	134	134	135
Adhocracy Culture	Pearson Correlation	.398**	1	.585**	.536**	.112
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.199
	N	132	134	133	133	134

Market Culture	Pearson Correlation	.394**	.585**	1	.570**	.184*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.032
	N	134	133	137	136	137
Hierarchy Culture	Pearson Correlation	.520**	.536**	.570**	1	.532
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	134	133	136	137	137
Turnover Intention	Pearson Correlation	-.547	.112	.184*	.532	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.199	.032	.000	
	N	135	134	137	137	138

Source: own survey, spss output

Regression Analysis

The data was analyzed using multiple linear regressions since the researcher is dealing with four forms of organizational culture as an independent variable and their separate relationships with the dependent variable. The assumptions for the multiple linear regressions were validated before starting the study.

The R values for evaluating the overall model fit may be found in the Model summary table. The R Square statistic demonstrates how much variation in the dependent variable, turnover intention, is explained by the independent variable, organizational culture. In this instance, the Turnover Intention dependent variable's variance is explained by the model in 36.4 percent of the cases. The corrected R Square is somewhat lower, showing that the model accounts for 35.2 percent of the variation.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.603	.364	.352	.84017	.364	24.339	4	125	.259

Source: own survey, spss output

Anova Analysis

While performing regression analysis, we examine the ANOVA table to see whether The Independent Variable and the Dependent Variable are connected. This may be regarded of as the regression model's overall fit. If indeed the F - statistics is meaningful, we may assume that the Independent Variables have a connection with the Dependent Variable when considered together. In just this situation, the F - statistics for regression analysis has a probability of 0.000, which is less than the level of significance of 0.05. As a result, we reject the hypothesis that the independent factors and the dependent variable have no connection.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	72.196	4	19.549	25.339	.000
	Residual	91.228	125	.710		
	Total	163.424	129			

Source: own survey, spss output

Coefficients

If Tolerance is less than .10 and VIF is less than 2.5, multicollinearity exists. All of the tolerance values are larger than .10, and the VIF is less than 2.5 in this scenario. We'll assume that multicollinearity isn't an issue.

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Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.415	.539		4.481	.000		
	Clan	-.382	.071	-.368	-5.150	.000	.716	1.396
	Adhocracy	-.031	.084	-.025	.214	.831	.582	1.717
	Market	.158	.087	.023	1.058	.292	.569	1.758
	Hierarchy	.369	.089	.357	4.481	.000	.548	1.826

Source: own survey, spss output

Hypothesis Testing

The regression coefficient, which represents the projected effect on the dependent variable with each predictor variables, is estimated in the output table above. We can observe that the beta coefficient for "Clan Culture" is significant and negative ($r = -0.382$ and $p = 0.00$). In the presence of clan culture, turnover intent is projected to drop by 37%.

Adhocracy Culture and Market Culture have positive coefficients, indicating a positive connection with the dependent variable. The significance value for variables, on the other hand, is higher than the alpha 0.52 and 0.23. We keep the hypothesis and conclude that these two factors have no meaningful link with the dependent variable. As a result of this data, we conclude that adhocracy and market culture are not important predictors of turnover intention.

Hierarchy culture has .000, which is lower Significance level than our alpha threshold of .05. When we examine at the coefficient, we can see that it is positive, implying that as organizations adopt culture type D, turnover will increase by 36.9%. As a result, we acknowledge that hierarchy culture is favorably and strongly associated to turnover intention.

Hypothesis	Result
H2: Clan Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.	Accepted
H3: Adhocracy Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.	Rejected
H4: Market Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.	Rejected
H5: Hierarchy Culture has a significant effect on turnover intention.	Accepted

CONCLUSION

Earlier studies looked at the link between organizational commitment and the likelihood of turnover (Wong, K. K. L., & Hui, S. C. N, 2015). The results show that organizational culture influences turnover intentions in both good and negative ways, which is consistent with findings from past studies (Kessler, 2015). Furthermore, the majority of the research I looked at were about other businesses or contact centers in other nations.

Clan organizational culture was shown to be adversely connected to turnover intention in the study. The kind of hierarchy culture was also associated to turnover, both positively and negatively, although adhocracy culture and market culture were not major contributors to the desire of private university personnel to leave.

The findings come to the fact that the primary cause of professional university staffs' voluntary turnover intentions is at the organizational level. The findings support some of the literature, which suggested that organizational culture is partly responsible for turnover intentions, as previously noted (Carmeli, 2005). It is somewhat true to the extent that not all forms of organizational culture have been proven to influence role ambiguity. The findings demonstrated that Type-A Clan and Type-D Hierarchy organizational cultures are substantially connected to the hypothesis and its influence on turnover intention.

The conclusions that Type-B Adhocracy and Type-C Market organizational cultures will increase voluntary turnover are unsupported. This indicates that defining goals as a method of motivating employees to meet corporate objectives has nothing to do with turnover intention and does not aid in the prevention of professional university staff turnover.

According to the poll, the Adhocracy culture is the most prevalent culture type in private universities. A perceived Clan culture type is less likely to create a turnover intention for the majority of responders. In other words, personnel are more inclined to commit to firms that value relationships.

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